
THE CONSTRUCTION OF REMEMBERING AND FORGETFULNESS: APPROACHES AND DISMISSES CONCERNING THE SPANISH CIVIL WAR

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Annual Meeting of The International Society of Political Psychology. Washington, July 1995.

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite the permanent remembering of the Spanish Civil War in the social imaginaire, if we leave historical studies aside, its investigation has not been the object of a noteworthy study in social science. This abandonment is in direct contrast to its stubborn emergence in the mass media. With the celebration of the 50th anniversary of the end of the Civil War coinciding with the centenary of General Franco's¹ birth, it seems that the attention of the media has somewhat awakened in the past decade. However, if we examine the bibliography it is clear that there is an almost complete underlying "**presentist conception**" of History, that is, a reading is made of the past through categories of the present. Obviously, this presentist conception gives legitimacy to a certain narrative conception in which all events become explanations of the process and this, in turn, seems to be submitted to a **truth regime**.

In fact, Spain has seen few processes which have generated so many interpretations and debates as the Civil War, a framework of feelings and intense experiences. It is full of polemical and controversial issues which are not only limited to a **historiographical viewpoint** and/or a **political dimension** but are also open to a **dimension of ethics** and **experience** which gathers the deepermost aspects of a conflict which transcends not only identification with one of the warring bands but also forms part of the most private side of personal experience.

¹One of the people directly responsible for the Spanish Civil War. Having participated in the conflict he became the military dictator who governed Spain from 1939 until his death in 1975.

Depending on the implicit or explicit ideological leaning of the historiographical studies of the Civil War, the results of the conflict are shown as obeying a careful plan previously designed to one end. Frequent omissions include the many different ups and downs, the unforeseeable accidents, the conditioned decisions and the situational confusion. The whole process is converted into the perfectly linked, modulated reply of a predetermined plan which always shows the when, who, how and what, and could not possibly have been changed by any event, all integrated in a sequence of events which appear as the fruit of infallible political calculations. In other words, the studies of the origins and the process are always discussed with respect to the results. The conception drawn up through the management of the process affects the process in the very moment it develops. It is therefore primordial to be aware of the versions passed down in order to gain a full awareness of the process.

And so it is very interesting to study the construction of remembering around the Civil War. It is not a simple process of evoking and recovering elements fixed in a historical moment but rather a remembering which produces narratives legitimizing, maintaining, ordering and conditioning social life. In other words, remembering brings about **normative** and **prescriptive** effects.

Before going further into our exposé, we should make it clear what conception of remembering we are going to use. We understand remembering to be knowledge of the past, not in the sense of the coincidence of memories with a preterite reality, but rather as a semantic ordering of events, a generative, non-mechanical reconstruction of such events, the obtention of narratives as a result of dialectics (Middleton and Edwards, 1990) and the negotiation of anti-ethical postures marked by a sense of the past.

2. PART I: THE CONSTRUCTION OF REMEMBERING AND FORGETFULNESS

2.1 Order of events and discursive unity

One general feature of dominant discourses on traumatic conflicts in the past is the use of argumentative repertoires and rhetorical strategies which favour the sketching and definition of a **presentist past**² to the detriment of social memory. They are also characterized by the legitimizing guarantee of a certain **social order**.

Remembering plays a determining rôle in this type of account and interpretations. As remembering and witnesses of the past increase and/or established order is questioned or even the remembering process becomes 'blurred' with time, we are faced with a conversion of remembering into History, in such a way that the past takes on an objective aspect and becomes reference to and confirmation of the natural superiority of the present.

This conversion of remembering into History obviously brings about a loss of confidence in people as it can question their ability and competence to produce discourses around the past; it also simultaneously makes them give in to the evidence (Pennebaker, 1990) of factual materialization ordered in accordance with the results of the present. In this way, the distance between the weight of the organized sequentializing of facts and the bringing together of the discourse in one whole single unit is made all the more obvious with the fragility of remembering, '*... which, contrary to historiography, reveals a clear taste for disorder and jumble; imitation and authenticity jostle here, all that is serious with what is futile, what is authentic with everything delirious or all that is prepared*' (Brossat, Combe, Potel and Szurek, 1990, p.40). Therefore, in the face of history, which directs its discourse at the present and future

²Particularly through explicit and formal explanations of the mass media, a vehicle of what may be thought, said or remembered.

by attempting to assure the perfect continuity in the future of the order it legitimizes, remembering defends a process of differentiation with respect to the present; as Chiara Sebastiani reminds us (1991), the act of remembering is, in this sense, a potentially subversive act.

As Paul Thompson (1978) suggests, all History is eventually dependent on its social purpose, being created even where it is non-existent. In this way, as Thompson assures us, there will be no question that the social purpose of History demands an understanding of the past which relates it directly or indirectly with the present.

Nevertheless, it is not possible to clarify or interpret a social phenomenon without explaining how it was constituted. Ibáñez (1989) states that the social phenomena 'themselves' have remembering, to the extent that they 'contain' the frameworks of the social relationships that instituted them and not only because they are relative to a specific historical period or because time has caused them to change. In fact, it might be said that *'... as happens with the future, the past is not "already written" either, given that its characteristics are brought up to date by specific later developments which, by definition, do not exhaust all the possibilities. It is no longer that the future partially depends on the past, but rather that the past acquires some of its features in accordance with the future which is effectively produced* (Ibáñez, 1989, p.111).

The recognition of this aspect is important in so far as it questions the objectiveness of psychosocial wisdom by placing it in society and not in the presumably stable discoveries to which standard historiography has us accustomed. Through this knowledge it is possible to consider the relevance of remembering, a relevance which is kept in check by the double character of process and product that any preterite event or process possesses. In a dialectic exchange this double character propitiates rereadings and reinterpretations of social practice, which at all times does not only favour the semantic and generative reorganization of the past, but also gives rise to the possibility of questioning the current social order. This is why it is **imperative** that the constituted social order must furnish remembering with logical consistence, that is, that subsequent facts must only be accessible through the reexamination of the occurrence of certain precedents. In other words, stories must be proscribed and History constructed in such a way that not only those who were present at the socio-historical moment of the event may have news of what 'really' happened, but that a specific 'discourse' may assure its future continuity.

However, the character given to a discourse does not proceed exclusively from the checking of the actual occurrence of the events themselves, but from the type of discourse (Calvo González, 1993; Lozano, 1987; White, 1987). In fact events appear as real because they are reminded and could be in one point of a chronological sequence, and not because they had really happen. It is not enough with a chronological account to consider them as historic. The possibility of being accounted in different ways make that, simultaneously, they could be taken as keys of reality or potentially false. For that reason, to be consider as historic, a fact must be susceptible of, at least, two accounts of its existence (White, 1987, p.34).

To a great extent, the importance of discourse is due to the fact that different events construct it, but at the same time, that discourse enables the constitution of the events which give it sense (Ricoeur, 1985). The 'narrative phrases,' as one of the different ways to describe the action (Lozano, 1987), gain special relevance in the conversion of remembering into History. These types of construction are characteristic and differentiate discourse from historical knowledge; they refer to at least two events separated in time, though they only describe the first of them (Danto, 1965).

Narrative phrases constitute one of the possible descriptions of an action but always depend on ulterior events unknown to the agents but which, on the other hand, are 'known' to the historian. The structure of the narrative phrase enables the description of events to be modified in accordance with what we know about ulterior events. As Simionescu and Padiou (1990) assure, when referring to the construction of the history of Rumania in the National Museum in Bucharest, *'... whoever controls the present does not only have the power to shape the future but also to remake the past* (Simionescu and Padiou, 1990, p.227).

However, why is it that the past is so important that there may be this greed for it? What is in play with the remembering of traumatic processes?

As we said at the beginning of this section, among the particular features of dominant discourses, the defence of presentist remembering and the legitimacy of a certain social order stand out. It is through this presentist remembering and the defence of a particular political system that the transit and conversion of remembering into History becomes possible.

After the Civil War, the totalitarian system based its legitimacy on the result of the conflict by operating on remembering in the way we have said. We are no longer dealing with the updating of shared events and the stabilizing of the chronological, ordered sequence of events which, from the first expression opened by the discourse, show their consummation, and in which witness is only borne to the 'truth' of what happened, the clinical asepsis of the facts.

2. The ends and the means; the establishment of the link between present and past.

The conversion of remembering into History and the inclusion of formulated, fixed ends in a narrative order must have an effect on society.

As Cornelius Castoriadis assures, '*... for all necessary, finished theology, everything is ruled from the end, postulated and determined from the beginning of the process by means of the postulation and determination of the means which will make it appear to have been done*' (Castoriadis, 1975, p.19). This is what is suggested by the dominant discourse circulating on the social circuit which relates the Civil War, its effects and democracy as the final outcome.

These considerations are certainly not trivial. Let us turn to the current political state in Spain, a system of parliamentary democracy. The *a priori* recognition of democracy as a desirable aim irrevocably sanctions the validity of certain meanings which were annulled in the process known as 'political transition,' some meanings being legitimized to the detriment of others. As Berger and Luckmann (1967) suggest, legitimation is not prescriptive just for persons actions, it also informs on the nature of things.

The discourse on the transition has a marked diacritical nature. It operates through a set of values (materialized in the defence of democratic order) which maintains a relationship of opposition to other possible sets of values. With this opposition, the revealing of the values posed in the discourse supposedly simultaneously expresses a commitment against other possible values. The most revealing expression may be recognised today in the daily discourses and practices which are more or less closely linked to State policy; we can appreciate in these, usually in larvate form, the effects of the confrontation of the Civil War.

The diacritical nature of these discourses enables us to point to a sequence in the development of the political system. The introduction of successive stages in time allows the 'progressiveness' of the system to be objectivized, and enables us to see how the system responds to a gradual passing through phases in a development directed at a final aim. This strategy of succession allows the present to be linked to the past and History to be ordered, as it includes all occurrences in society within the framework of one coherent unit full of meaning. A discourse on the past is offered thus, in which what is tacit in current practice is made explicit (Taylor, 1984) and acts in the future as a referential framework for individual action.

It is equally relevant to examine the predominant discourse on History given in different political processes, where the object to be explained is made to seem the protagonist; however, this protagonism acts as a legitimizing element and shows that the process is verified. In fact, History is not presented as a framework but rather, from a narrative distance, a **hegemonic discourse** is drawn up on History which is basically **self-referring**. Here, the legitimacy of one specific political model appears as a synonym of social legitimization. Obviously, this self-referring construction of History and its legitimization act as guarantors of historical continuity through the framework of social discourses, and produce social effects which impose a system of images, reminders and forgettings (Páez; Insúa and Vergara, 1992) on the remembering of the period, acting in such a way as to facilitate the Governability favoured by a 'legitimized present' in which norms and democracy stand out as common sense.

Democracy as "common sense" (Íñiguez and Vázquez, 1992) implies that groups and collectives have knowledge which works in terms of evidence and consensus. It is here that we find the diacritical nature of democracy. In fact, in this way we establish how things happen and must happen, which enables us both to explain why things have happened and determine their appearance.

It is of use to make a parallel analysis of all of the conceptual terminology as on many occasions it goes beyond mere description and becomes the epicentre of discourses and propitiator of practices. By way of example, consider the concept of "**consensus**" which was used generously during the years of the Spanish transition (del Águila and Montoro, 1984) and even after the transition as a discursive bridge between the Civil War and the current political system (Íñiguez and Vázquez, 1995). It has, in this way, been the source of other concepts, and more importantly, it has weighed heavily on practices, evolution, exchanges and the styles of both public and anonymous actors. It was therefore one of the main keys to the 'management' of the transition and, of course, the negotiation or, more exactly, the **pact on the past**; *'It is a point [the past] which, in short, tends to be made obvious in political discourse. The concealing is based on a previously, implicitly, agreed terrain to confront new problems from different angles'* (del Águila and Montoro, 1984, p.253). In other words, it is a pact on what has to be remembered and what should be forgotten, which includes the Civil War, postwar oppression and the ostracism to which any discourse directly or indirectly striking any aspect related to the conflict is subjected.

3. PART II: THE SPANISH CIVIL WAR BETWEEN REMEMBERING AND HISTORY.

3.1 How "ordinary people" remember history.

In the second part of this chapter, we develop some of the most relevant results of one of the empirical studies we have made around the social construction of the remembering of the Spanish Civil War.

We believe that we should establish a conceptual distinction between remembering and History. Remembering refers to different nominal narratives of the events which occurred between 1936 and 1939. History corresponds to the process of conversion of these narratives into the reified, institutionalized History of the period.

This difference is similar to the one developed by Connerton (1989). This author makes an explicit difference between social memory and historical reconstruction. One of the specific bases which distinguishes the two concepts is that historical reconstruction is basically what professionals of History do when they search for and identify traces of past events. This effect is closely related to the authority they gleam from an activity which is characterized as being scientific. We have tried to go further by identifying another, maybe more fundamental, base; the ideological and political effects.

The same author has suggested that historical reconstruction is independent from social memory in the sense that even what has been forgotten may be rediscovered by History, while he admits at the same time that any historical reconstruction may be strengthened by the social memory of groups, as is, for instance, the case of oral history. We have, once again, wished to go further on this point and give credit to the added value in terms of the understanding of social and political action, of social memory.

With these parameters, the design of our empirical investigation is synthesized in two useful analyses:

The first consists of the apprehension of **narratives** through recourse to oral history or another technique which brings out the experiences of the protagonists in the process.

The second consists of the apprehension of **remembering**, with the use of two kinds of analytical tools:

a.- those which give access to discourses circulating socially.

b.- those which enable the remembering of the population to be identified.

Obviously these views are neither incompatible nor exclusive. In this chapter, we will only deal with the second of them, **the analysis of the concept which 'ordinary people' currently have of this historical process.**

3.2 Rewriting remembering: the Spanish Civil War of young students.

In this section, we present one of the empirical approaches to the narratives on the definition of the Spanish Civil War circulating among a very specific population, the students of the Autonomous University of Barcelona. Some of the aspects we have commented on in previous sections are illustrated. To this end we have designed a study with the purpose of initiating a useful analytical mechanism to gain access to the processes of remembering and reminder of the Spanish Civil War.

There were two basic aims in the analysis want to develop here:

- To identify the elements or bases through which different discourses on the Spanish Civil War are driven as they circulate on the social circuit.

- To identify the characteristic elements and establish the different positions from where the aforesaid discourses are made.

We used a survey method in the study. A questionnaire was administrated consisting of four totally open-ended questions. Although the main argument directing the survey was the analysis of the Spanish Civil War, only the first question dealt with the subject directly:

How would you explain what the Spanish Civil War was to a person who did not know?"

Because of a study made in parallel on "the Spanish Political Transition" this question was accompanied by another posed in similar terms but directed at this subject. The two remaining questions ask about more specific points which constitute dimensions of the discourse on and in democracy, and about political ideology. The survey was carried out in a totally anonymous manner. The only personal information requested was age, sex and the faculty where the person studied.

Although there is obviously mutual influence between the four questions, as they generate a particular interrogative context, we will not stop here to analyze their meaning and incidence, which does not mean that they should not be borne in mind.

The survey was made on a sample of 313 third year psychology students in the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.

3.2.1. Procedure of analysis

The results were obtained by the statistical and lexicometric package SPAD_T³ (Bécue, 1991) which enables automatic content analysis of textual information. The operations are part of the conglomerate of techniques known as "Automatic Analysis of Texts and Discourses" which designates a group of systematic methods through which it is possible to **describe**, **synthesize** and **classify** textual information independently of its features or source. The main aim of most of these methods is to produce an exhaustive description and/or systematic ordering of the body of a text which is both descriptive and statistical.

The method we have used was specially inspired in Data Analysis, as conceived by the French school of statistics (Benzecri, 1973) and is based on the use of statistical procedures such as Factor Analysis of Correspondence and Hierarchical Classification of statistical subjects, which allow different indexes to be calculated to obtain a synthesis and categorization of text variability. This type of analysis facilitates the treatment of a large amount of text data, which would otherwise be difficult to deal with (Lebart, Salem, 1988).

In order to be able to apply these analyses to text information, it is necessary to create different types of contingency tables depending on the information being handled and on the analyses being applied ("*Replies x Lexical Forms*"; "*Lexical Forms x texts*", etc.). It is possible to apply the **Factor Analysis of Simple Correspondence** to these tables, as well as the **Automatic Classification** methods.

The **Factor Analysis** describes large tables of data by projecting them on a space of n dimensions which retains a large amount of the original information.

The **Classification** synthesizes data by grouping from different homogeneous classes into individual groups from the information available.

These analyses may be complemented by **lexicometrical methods** such as **Alphabetical Glossaries**, the **Concordances**⁵ between lexical forms or the selection of **Replies and Characteristic Lexical Forms**⁶ which make up the body of the analysis.

3.2.2. Description of results

³Système Pourtable pour l'Analyse des Données Textuelles.

⁴'**Lexical Form**' refers to a group of characters between two separators, to distinguish it from 'word' for those of us who maintain the sense given to it by Grammar. '**Text**' refers to a group of lexical forms.

⁵Presentation of the context in which determined lexical forms are found.

⁶'Lexical Forms' or groups of them which present a statistically significant rate of appearance.

Four groups of information were obtained through statistical analysis using the SPAD_T package:

- a) a general, lexicometrical description of the components shaping the corpus under study,
- b) information on the conceptions of the Spanish Civil War,
- c) information classifying individuals according to most characteristic replies, and
- d) a third set of information allowing us to obtain the categorization of different lexical forms.

a) Lexicometrical Analysis

The total number of replies was 313. The total number of words collected was 16,190, of which 2,461 were different. For analysis, words appearing 20 times or more were selected in order to enable the statistical calculations. The final corpus of the analysis was made up of 14,006 words.

b) Conceptions on the Spanish Civil War

The organization of the information available on the conceptions of the Civil War were analyzed by means of a contingency table of "Individuals x Words" (n=313 individuals and p=87 words). The initial table was submitted to an Analysis of Simple Correspondence which provided us with 6 factors⁷. However, interpretation could only be made of the first four which, as a group, explain 15.64% of the variance. The interpretation of each was carried out from the absolute and relative contributions of each word to each factor.

The following four polarities were identified:

Polarity 1: Causes vs. Effects

The first factor (Own value: 0.2719, Explained percentage of variance: 4.05%) shows the polarity between the identifiable causes of the Civil War and the effects it had.

⁷The percentages of explanation of the variance are very 'conservative' but this is due to the nature of the table and does not affect the interpretability the solution (Benzecri, 1973).

Polarity 2: Agency vs. Victimization

The second factor (Own value: 0.2158, Explained percentage of variance: 3.22%) distinguishes between the identification of responsibility and protagonism, and the effects that the protagonism of the conflict has on people.

Polarity 3: Reconstruction vs. Objectivization

The third factor (Own value: 0.1972, Explained percentage of variance: 2.94%) shows the polarity between the elements rebuilding imagination of the conflict against the elements which specify and place it in History.

Polarity 4: Identification vs. Experience

The fourth factor (Own value: 0.1860, Explained percentage of variation: 2.77%) distinguishes between subjects victimized in the imagination of the war and the elements which identify, store, describe and shape the real experience of the event.

c) Classification of individuals

To enable identification and definition of the different kinds of reply, as well as the 'possible' ascription of these replies to categories of individuals, we have undertaken their classification.

This classification gave us the identification of six groups whose description was made by using the replies and the characteristic lexical forms in each as a criterium.

Group 1: Chroniclers

A group of people characterized by their direct, first mention of the chronological moment of the development of the conflict. They relate a series of events which frequently do not coincide with the succession of facts registered by history. They give simultaneous explanations accompanying the story of what happened in time.

The Civil War began in Africa, among the army which was then fighting to maintain the lands which theoretically belonged to Spain. General Franco, together with other members of the high command of the army, came to Spain in order to gain power. They reached Madrid, deployed troops and invaded the Government. General Franco proclaimed himself Head of the Spanish State but the East of Spain rose up against this proclamation (Aragon, Valencia, Navarre... the 'Reds'.) and they declared war on Franco's troops. The war lasted three years (1936-1939) and ended with the victory of Franco (the 'Nationals'). The Nationals had right wing policies and governed as a dictatorship for about 40 years.

Group 2: Objectivists

This group puts emphasis on the takeover of Government and generally makes precise reference to the dates of the conflict. They occasionally point to the Franquist Dictatorship as the cause of the Civil War and give some information about the participation of other countries in the conflict, generally lauding one of the contending sides.

It was an armed conflict which began on the 18th July 1936 and ended in each area of Spain when the victorious army went in (normally in 1939). The causes were political; the rebellion of a series of generals (among them the one who would become Head of State, "Caudillo" Franco) against the II Spanish Republic. It seems that this uprising was caused by the remembering of the chaotic I Republic and also because the government in power since 1931 had not solved the problems of the international economic situation caused by the 'crash' in 1929. The rebels, or nationals, crossed the straight with their troops (of the Moroccan army) and from the beginning gained the support of most of the West of Spain. They received help from other fascist governments of the time (Germany and Italy) and received the passive support of the remaining western democracies. On the other hand, the Republican Government, despite having one of the most advanced constitutions of the time, only received help from the USSR. Finally a fascist dictatorship was imposed for 40 years.

Group 3: Antagonists

People who offer an explanation for the Civil War in terms of confrontation between groups for ideological reasons. They make some descriptions of the consequences of the conflict.

The Spanish Civil War was a conflict between two groups which had very different ideologies. Some were right wing monarchists and the others left wing republicans. Unfortunately for the country, the monarchists and fascists won pushing the population into a long period of dictatorship and repression. There were more reds in the north of Spain than in the centre and the south.

Group 4: Deideologizers

The discourse of this group basically emphasizes the affective derivations of the conflict. Their interventions on the reasons for the Civil War seem to lack any kind of ideological argument.

I would say that it was a huge negative event which marked the existence of those who had the misfortune of living through it and that even today there is still 'waste' (same as influences) from what happened then between people and above all, on a general level in Spanish society. If we could measure how absolutely negative it was, we would truly understand that it must not happen again (as it is repeated in other places) either here in Spain or in any place.

Group 5: Polarizers

A group of people that recognizes, generally without naming, two groups in the contention and a group of causes discharged ideologically but with heavy affective connotations, which allude to a series of reasons that, in their opinion, explain the conflict.

The truth is that not even I can explain the Spanish Civil War. Like in all wars, it was a conflict of interests; on one hand, a dictator, General Franco, with all the army backing him; on the other all those who opposed another dictatorship. Apart from this, I suppose there were other factors, such as economic, social etc. But the truth is that I don't really know what happened. The thing is the two sides went to war. Many people died on both sides (all Spanish citizens). The franco partisans were much better trained, they were the army, and

they ended up winning and imposing a dictatorship (that few people wanted) which did not come to an end until 30 years later.

Group 6: Philohistorians

A group which makes a description based on the chronological succession of identifiable historiographical elements. On occasions the statements and explanations are of a certain ideological nature, though most usually the expressions are objective.

The Spanish Civil War occurred at the beginning of the 20th Century when, following a political crisis, two very different ideological groups were formed in Spain. The first group defended democracy at all costs and the others believed that the best thing for the country to work well was the forming of a Republic. The War lasted three years (from 1936 to 1939) and during this period there was an atmosphere of tension in the whole country as a direct consequence of the situation of fighting between people of the same country that maybe before had been colleagues, neighbors ... and who at this time were killing each other for the sake of ideological questions. The war affected everyone, from very small children to adults who were forced to intervene. The victory of the Republicans was compensated, for this group, by the figure of the dictator Franco, although after him appeared what we would call democracy, as seen through the monarchy in the figure of King Juan Carlos.

d) Classification of words.

Thematic analysis of the replies, carried out by classifying the lexical forms, has also demonstrated the convenience of extracting 6 configured categories of the various options of the Spanish Civil War:

Category 1: Chronological

This category of answers explicitly recognizes the confrontation (*Civil War, Spanish, conflict, regime*), emphasizes the time aspect (*three, were, years, lasted*), chronologically identifies the limits of the conflict (*1936, 1939, 1936-1939*) and refers to the participants (*Band, nationals, right winders, politicians, Franco, republicans*).

Category 2: Conflictual

These replies are characterized by their spontaneous reference recognizing the existence of contending elements (*bands, side, two, other, others*), their mention and ideological identification (*reds, fascists*) and the explicitness of their connections (*fight, confrontation*).

Category 3: Characterizing

These bring together all the concepts which usually shape the discourse referring to the origin (*coup d'état, army, Franco, Republic, military*) and development of the Civil War (*when, all, politics, people, Spanish, situation, government, moment*).

Category 4: Affective

This category includes all the terms and concepts which allude to an emotional translation of the conflict, such as, for instance, *brothers*.

Category 5: Polarizing

The participants in this category allude to the specific fact of the War (*war, country, period, politicians*) and to the confrontation between two opposing positions (*different, they, people, his/her, groups, their, all*).

Category 6: History-making

This is a category of words which recognizes the existence of ideas in conflict (*ideas, ideologies, same*), translated into personal confrontation (*people, policies*).

4. CONCLUSIONS

With our question we hoped to identify the main narratives on the Spanish Civil War which would put us in touch with the discourse, or discourses, given in society about the event. What we obtained was a configuration of bases which offers us an approximation of great heuristic power, to describe and understand them. In this way, the 'continual' "causes vs. effects", "agency vs. victimization", "reconstruction vs. objectivization", "identification vs. experience", configure narratives which we have been able to classify as: chronological, conflictual, characterizing, affective, polarizing and history-making.

These different narratives, and it is here that our work shows most coherence with respect to the hypotheses of Halbwachs (1950), concern different social groups. Aside from the interest that the identification of these groups which maintain different positions might have (their sociological and demographical characteristics, etc.), it is true that they could easily be recognized and clear differences could be shown. Later studies should eventually lead us to a detailed description of the correspondences between narratives and social groups or categories.

This would, therefore, be a useful work, as it is through their belonging to a social group that individuals participate in the building of remembering. On this point we share the viewpoint of Connerton (1989) when he states that the idea of an individual memory completely separate from social memory is a meaningless abstraction. Nevertheless, the most important implication of this statement is that the different social groups, categories and collectives, each with its own past, will surely have different social memories which shape and are shaped by their own intersubjectivity. Every memory, as personal as it may be, even of events which are private and strictly personal and have not been shared with anyone, exists through its relationship with what has been shared with others: language, idiom, events etc. everything which shapes the society of which we form a part.

In our initial discussion, we also sought the connection with ideology and political action. Remembering has something to do with both. We have maintained that the fundamental relationship is related to legitimization, and more specifically with the legitimization of the democratic order. Therefore, one of the consequences of the gradual conversion of social memory into History is the considering of the democratic order as the context which reduces the conflict, the fight, that the War represents. Another consequence is undoubtedly the presentation of a social context of continuity in time which favours identity as a collective unit and restates progressiveness and, as a result, the firm unity between collectives and the political system. This unity is guaranteed by the objectivization of certain enemies from the past which must be fought in order to maintain the system, an aspect which falls back once again on legitimacy.

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